

Dis-affirming mathematics education practices: An edutopía in Colombia

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The process of building an academic community of mathematics educators, concerned with issues of social, cultural and political nature within a developing country like Colombia is a hard endeavour, that demands to address and embodying critical stances in several ways. This paper reports and analyses the experiences of a Colombian research group in mathematics education (EdUtopía) are discussed, in order to elucidate some of the theoretical and methodologies findings achieved as a group, as well as the challenges and consequences that arise when the paradigms of a conservative academic community are called into question. Three aspects of the group's journey are highlighted: their integration process, the initiatives and forms of organization they have had up to now, and the impact and reception of their work.

The desire of make a contribution to the formation of critical citizens for a democratic and peaceful society, while working as mathematics teacher is a complex matter in a country like Colombia, since the national research tradition in the field is still ill-grounded and fundamentally guided by a diffusionist conception of science development, that assumes a colonial scheme of center-periphery (Matharan, 2016), in which local researchers role is reduced to receive, import, translate and apply notions, theories and methods created by others coming from a “civilized” society. As a result of such conception, the majority of the mathematics education (EM) research in our country focuses its efforts on teaching decontextualized content, with practical purposes of merely improving scores on international standardised tests and mainly under cognitive approaches¹.

We want to share our attempts to break the referred colonial scheme. To do so, this text reports experiences of our research group in mathematics education (EdUtopía), that works since the last 12 years under approaches of social, cultural and political nature. We analyse

¹ We refer to Flórez & Céspedes (2019), García (2014), Jaramillo (2014), León (2014), Ortiz (2014) and Gómez (2000) as previous overviews of the colombian community of mathematics education researchers.

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the theoretical and methodologies that have been used, as well as the challenges and consequences that our displacements of tradition implied. This text presents three aspects of EdUtopía's becoming: our integration process, the initiatives and forms of organization we have had so far, and the impact and reception of our work within the Colombian educational community.

We contend that studying the trajectory of a research group in mathematics education that runs counter to a hegemonic trend serves to create strategies, sub-versions and alternatives, by seeking a mathematical education that have in its horizon a critical democracy with social justice, in pursuit of a well-being that counterbalance individualistic and economic rationalities

De-formation

When the research group was constituted in 2009, all the members of the EdUtopía research group were mathematics teacher educators at the Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas (UDFJC), in its undergraduate and graduate programmes. In particular. The undergraduate program provides a university degree in education, and is considered atypical when compared with other mathematics teacher training programmes in Colombia, due to its intended classroom work methodology (oriented towards problem solving) and also for its curricular structure. Such training programme is, in itself, a curricular research project, organised by four problematic/thematic cores that aim to train teachers-as-researchers in a wholistic way, distancing itself from other programmes whose teacher training interests are more mathematically oriented.

The program problematic/thematic cores are: School Mathematics, Advanced Mathematical Thinking, Professional Contexts and Teaching Practice. Through each one of them, the program is driven with/towards a high social and political sensibility. It is important to highlight that this social sense used to be fostered in a general way by teacher educators with a human sciences background, linked to the Professional Contexts core, who were not necessarily trained in mathematics. It was not clear how the pre-service teachers managed to relate mathematics to their own experience. This gap led to the possibility of creating EdUtopía as research group, aiming to reflect on those issues from a Critical Mathematical Education perspective.

EdUtopía began as a group of colleagues and friends, with relatively similar initial backgrounds –mathematicians or mathematics educators– from public universities in the capital of Colombia, with research interests in mathematics education and with an inclination towards socio-cultural and political aspects of mathematics teacher education: ethnomathematics, the history of mathematics, the philosophy of mathematics, the didactics of mental operations, the incorporation of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in mathematics education. Some of our previous work experiences were developed around segregated communities, where we realise that social issues emerging from grassroots organisational processes in communities were not addressable from the cognitive approaches, because such approaches imagined improvement of education only as a matter

of improving teaching. The approach to social issues, the need for collaborative work that support communities' agendas, as well as the willingness to think about citizenship education within the mathematics classroom, forged our interests.

This kick-starter point brings us to a new field of work that became a line of research within the UDFJC. We initially took references in the ideas of researchers such as Alan Bishop, Ubiratan D'Ambrosio, Orlando Fals Borda, Paulo Freire, Ole Skovsmose and Paola Valero. As the EdUtopía research group, we discussed statements from critical mathematics education such as "the social precedes the mathematical", "everything educational (or everything human) is social" or "mathematics is a non-neutral knowledge", which we still find revealing and challenging for the field of teacher education. Thus, in the EdUtopía research group:

- We began to incorporate ideas into the different training spaces of the undergraduate or graduate courses that each one was in charge of, even when such spaces were fundamentally disciplinary in mathematics, forcing us to make it clear that the socio-political training of future mathematics teachers it is not a question of context, but structural and linked to mathematics itself.
- We sought alternative methodological horizons of work, different from those that were customary in research groups (v.gr. the use of control and experimental groups with rigid planning), due to our inclination towards contemporary methods of social research and our disengagement with positivist research.
- We discuss ideas with other research groups at the UDFJC and other universities, with the aim of contrasting views on the objects of research, incorporating a closer relationship between objects and subjects of research, employing more reflexive methods and having purposes that could be more sensitive of the social impacts of research.
- We directed last year student's projects, based on a principle of horizontality in which pre-service teacher and teacher educators were academic peers, not directors and supervisors. We worked on concrete problems experienced by the future teachers when they made their practicum and internships
- We interacted with in-service teachers, from different parts of the country, having a direct impact on classrooms and their contexts, reporting results in different sets of publications.
- Former pre-service teachers created their own collectives of teachers on critical perspectives, maintaining spaces for communication with Edutopía.
- We continued graduate studies as personal initiatives, at master's and doctoral level, according to our own specific theoretical interests within the social, cultural and political aspects of mathematics education.

One of the first places we created as a group was a reading seminar. This seminar was later joined by students interested in participating in the group's activities. When one of our colleagues ran an elective course on Ethnomathematics, we went on a field trip to the region

of Tierradentro, one of the settlements of the Nasa indigenous community. We did not go there to teach or to impose agendas or methods, but rather to learn about their forms of organisation and interaction through assemblies, which is highly influential to our own group structure.

After a couple of months, we proposed a research project entitled “Learning milieus as a Critical Mathematics Education proposal in the professional development of in-service mathematics teachers” and worked with a group of mathematics teachers from a public school in Bogotá, the Colegio Distrital Paulo Freire. On this experience:

The group of teachers met weekly for a year, to discuss and reflect on the educational practices of many teachers at school, and on how these practices reduces mathematical knowledge only to the disciplinary, prioritising the use of algorithms and detaching such knowledge from any context. (Leal & Torres, 2011, p. 8, our translation).

In addition to the final report of the project, several of the reflections that emerged from these meetings were subsequently published by the participating teachers, with whom learning milieus were constructed to address social problems perceived in the school (Ángel & Camelo, 2010; Cardozo, Chaparro, & Mancera, 2010; Leal & Torres, 2011; Mancera-Ortiz, Camelo & González-Alvarado, 2015; Sánchez & Torres, 2009). Years later, these teachers still remember the experience with the EdUtopía research group and point to it as the most significant among those they have lived through, due to the lasting impact on their classrooms, the ways of participation that were provided and the type of collaborative relationship that was built there.

Up to this point there were no stumbling blocks. However, the invention of new forms of group organisation also brought with it many challenges and disagreements, failures, discarded experiments, and a certain loss of momentum. These inventions and its pitfalls are related in the following section.

Dis-organisation

Our ways of working have changed substantially during these 13 years. Although we initially assumed the usual dynamics of collectively executing a project (Leal & Torres, 2011), later we incorporated criticism of the way we carry out our own work and ventured into various forms of group production: reading seminars on theoretical foundations of critical mathematics education, joint writing and cross-review exercises, which produced some texts (see Sánchez & Torres, 2009; Mancera-Ortiz, Camelo, & González-Alvarado, 2015). In 2017 we decided to hold a series of remote meetings with colleagues from other groups and universities to discuss cross-cutting issues of importance for critical perspectives. In each meeting we addressed a particular topic, sharing elements from personal research experiences and then exchanging the reflections we have made on the subject, seeking to establish affinities, differences or even divergences between positions.

There were initiatives that finally did not materialise, such as the writing of the proceedings of the remote meetings, the hosting of academic events in alternative spaces and formats, and the establishment of cooperative alliances with research groups from another

country. In the period from 2015 to 2020, the group adopted a new strategy in order to provide support to the doctoral studies that four of us started: we undertook exercises of active listening, collaboration, commented on individual productions, as well as work in subgroups (Parra et al., 2017; Marcone et al., 2019).

Now more recently, after getting our doctoral degrees, we have promoted academic meetings between master's students that we advise in our universities (Universities of Cauca and UDFJC). In these meetings, our current and former students have interacted as academic peers of colleagues in other universities, a circumstance that has allowed exchanges of ideas and positions on mathematics education from their own teaching experiences.

It is possible to identify common elements in all the forms of work that we have undertaken: a) the horizontality, b) the plurality of individual sensibilities and interests, c) the intense debate that the proposals entail, d) the fraternal spirit in carrying out the debates, and e) the back and forth between theory and practice.

Our commitment to *horizontality* questions the endogamy and hierarchy that we observe as habitual and established in training and research spaces of Colombian mathematics education. We decided not to embrace working and organisational schemes in which a "principal" researcher decides the group's research agenda and acts as its spokesperson. Our working sessions can include the presence of undergraduate, postgraduate students and invited colleagues, seeking to take care to assign the same responsibilities and times for the construction of arguments. This way of working demands more time in decision-making, because we work and discuss until we reach consensus and collaborations. Leaderships are transitory and always limited to specific and circumstantial activities. Another consequence of this absence of a centralised spokesperson is that there is practically no presence in institutionalised or administrative spaces. Membership and permanence in the group is not seen as a tool for obtaining institutional rewards (which in Colombia ensures workload time or funding for research projects).

Regarding the *plurality of individual sensibilities/interests*, it is important to mention that EdUtopia does not operate as a study group dedicated to the work of any particular author or pre-established concept. The criterion of relevance to discuss or not a topic or author does not include anything than its potential to address social concerns about mathematics and its teaching. EdUtopia's current research agenda is the result of a combination of interests and approaches that go through the philosophy of mathematics, ethnomathematics, the philosophy of difference, the constitution of subjectivities and mathematical modelling. The most visible consequence of this combination is a kind of conceptual and methodological indefiniteness, which, far from being a symptom of stylistic dilettantism or eclecticism, is a sign of openness and intellectual curiosity. We assume ourselves to be akin to, but not pigeonholed with, socio-cultural and political approaches to mathematics education. EdUtopia is conceived as an agora, an open stage in which to communicate our changing concerns.

The notion of critique is central to the group not only as a theoretical notion, but also as a working precept. The *intense* (and sometimes merciless) *debate* of postulates and arguments

has characterised us, to the point of creating an internal dynamic that could not be followed by some members who chose to leave the group. We seek to embody critique in terms not only of elaborating critiques, or to address situations of crises in the practices of mathematics or mathematics education in the contexts in which we are in the world, but also as an awareness towards the limits and conditionings of research practice itself.

For us, critique comprises, among other things, the attitude of problematising, questioning, illuminating the blindspots of what appears to us as mathematics educators as normal, good, necessary, neutral and unproblematic. When a member wants to work on a paper or a project, they know that they can rely on the others to find weaknesses and omissions in the theoretical and methodological decisions. The passage of time and several episodes of confrontation and conflict have led us to assume our fierce character, not as something automatically harmful, but as a mechanism to elaborate our ideas.

The *fraternal spirit* is the flip side of the feisty character. Members have established relationships of friendship, support and affection that have helped us to strengthen each other and to deal with the heat of certain discussions in a depersonalised way, as well as to establish a space for companionship in the face of the loneliness and competitiveness of our professional practice as academics. Life's adversities have also been a space for expressing solidarity among us.

Our conception of critique as a working value is also visible in our actions to subject the academic discussions of a theoretical-methodological nature to the contrast with school practices. This implies a *two-way exercise*, where practice and theory are mutually challenged. We have made this exercise concrete through a frequent search for articulation with international and local academic communities, where we invite colleagues from other groups, backgrounds and workplaces to debate our ideas, as a way to counteract the atomisation and insularity of academic productions. We have experiences of collaboration with rural and urban teachers' collectives for periods of more than 10 years, without the need to be executing a funded project or even without the aim of producing an academic paper. These collaborations are given under the premise of considering the teacher as an intellectual pair who can and should raise theoretical reflections, which is why we have co-written articles and papers with in-service teachers. Conversely, we also participate in academic spaces in which we try to address tensions and concerns arising from teaching practice, under the premise that theory must deal with the here and now of educational realities.

Dis-approval

Assuming our affinity with socio-cultural and political approaches to mathematics education has allowed us to be critical of theories that systematically ignore "those at the bottom of the social fabric". Such systematicity is an inconvenient practice, since it has served to invisibilise, hide or disfigure the reality of the social, cultural and political problems experienced in Colombian society (and in other developing ones). This affinity goes hand in hand with the idea of thinking the right to education under the conception of its possible

recipients, assumed as “those from below”, those from the periphery, the inferior ones, or, as Galeano (1971) would say, “the nobodies”. They are part of the new social, racial and gender segregation, since our school system has been built taking as a reference its addressees – workers, poor, peasants, blacks, etc, but assumed as inferior in the power-knowing-being scale.

Aligned to that, we consider that we must be cautious to not fall into the historical dynamic in which the State has served, as a tool or instrument, to exercise class hegemony (Haya de la Torre, 1994). It is time that, among all of us, we give ourselves the opportunity to think about our countries, and this implies accepting that the educational demands and needs of today’s population are different from those that the classical educational offer has met. In this respect, Tenti-Fanfani (2005) mentions:

Today, the educational demands and needs of the population are different. Differences of all kinds (ethnic, cultural, social, gender, etc.) tend to be asserted and seen as legitimate, and different aspirations cannot be satisfied by a simple expansion of classical educational provision. (p. 20, our translation).

From this perspective, questions arise such as: what does it mean to meet the educational demands and needs –in mathematics education– of the current Colombian population? In what ways does mathematics education facilitate or impede the construction of a critical democracy in Colombian society? What forms of work emerge in/among the communities² with whom we share?

Meeting these demands has led us to have a constant struggle against the status quo of mathematics education in Colombia, which maintains that any educational proposal must focus its interest on school mathematics content established as common, generalised, standardised, and susceptible to being measured by international tests; this content favours the handling of procedures and algorithms deprived of context and sense, even without noticing who will be the recipients of such an educational proposal. In contrast, within the group we consider the social to be a fundamental aspect of learning mathematics. We understand the social as the possibility of bringing –with the students– problematic situations associated with the micro/macro context of those who learn, to be studied collectively within the educational institution and supported by mathematics, in order to interpret and re-interpret such situations.

That insight led us to another consideration: in order to pose situations of interest to learners, we must know who our students are, which brings with it an inquiry into the contexts in which they find themselves, perform and live together. Such knowledge is not a superficial or geographical matter; it also refers to the deep social, cultural and political relationships and interweavings that embody multiple historical moments.

Therefore, we distanced ourselves from positions that consider students as universal and cognitive subjects, who by the fact of being in a classroom are ready to learn mathematical knowledge. On the contrary, we understand that our students are more than a homogenised

² Groups of in-service and pre-service teachers, indigenous people, students and parents across the country.

body, that they are in constant relationship with others, that they are subjects with likes, dislikes, desires and dispositions, who sometimes distance themselves from the act of knowing from the academic mathematical logic.

We consider that our starting point must take into account the knowledge of our students and their social, cultural, historical and political context that conditions their lives, from which we must raise, as teachers, specific problems or topics that emphasise the responsibility of students as citizens. This is concretised in the possibility of participating in an informed way in the making of decisions that affect us all, making use of mathematical tools and in the pursuit of social justice.

The interest in the relation between mathematics and social context has placed us in a dual scenario, as we assume a permanent confrontation of arguments between those who consider viable approaches to socio-cultural and political approaches to mathematics education such as ours (approval) and, at the same time, with those who reject it (disapproval).

It is enough to see how many of the teachers who are in the process of continuing their training process (in postgraduate studies, for example) see themselves identified with our approach, given their daily experiences at the schools³. We are not unaware that there has been a certain “boom” among Colombian mathematics educators, either by approaching the socio-cultural and political perspectives of mathematics education, or by trying to give arguments such as “all didactics is social”, or “all mathematics is social”, given that they admit that their usual approaches have lacked this analysis, and realise that questions about the critical and citizenship education being done through mathematics are increasingly emerging with force.

Convergent statements from school teachers contrasts with the positions of academic colleagues in our national community, who state that the social is important (as a meaningless catch-all phrase) but who claim that it is our only duty to focus on disciplinary and didactic mathematical knowledge, keeping disciplinary knowledge in a preponderant status in the educational process, insofar as it is necessary and sufficient to empower those who learn it. There are others who position themselves by pointing out that the social aspect is important, but optional for the mathematics teacher, placing the social aspect in the background, even in a condition of elusive and/or postponable, as if it were not a constituent dimension of educational action. Is it visible how re-emerges the traditional perspective of knowledge as disembodied, universal and hegemonic, which colonises and superimposes itself on other knowledge forms.

Dis-considerations

In the previous sections we have recounted our attempts to do practice and research in mathematics education in unconventional ways that escape the narrow frameworks of a

³ For example, they share our view that students are much more than cognitive subjects, and that it is therefore important to consider the social, cultural and political context that surrounds them.

tradition present in academic and professional bodies. This search is motivated by a conscious and public stance on our social agency as mathematics educators and has led us to question aspects that are taken as natural and resolved, such as the relationships with the groups that are investigated, the particular conceptions about the very purpose of the field of mathematics education and the role of the researcher. Our stance on these aspects has enabled us to learn and achieve things that would have been unattainable within the established models of research practice. At the same time, we have had to deal with the consequences of going against the tides.

With regard to relations with the groups being researched, in contrast to certain forms of academic extractivism, where communities are approached to obtain data for imposed and circumstantial research, we have chosen to: a) have more direct, in-depth and continuous contact with the different actors involved in the research, b) to visit their territories guided by them, recognising situations that they consider as critical, and c) to make them participants in the decisions on the topics, methods and results of the research, calling for collective reflections on the impact of the experience on the transformation of the chosen situations.

We believe that conceiving the field of mathematics education as devoted to the finding and reporting of “successful” experiences that can demonstrate progress in the quest for the improvement of teaching conveys the assumption of a non-existent homogeneity of the students and their educational realities and, ultimately, implies a delimitation of mathematics education that we find exhausted and inappropriate for realities such as Colombia’s. We have responded to this reduction with a vindication of the heterogeneity of the individuals, interests and living conditions that inhabit the communities. In turn, this has led us to recognise the usefulness of reporting all experiences, whether or not they fit into the established concept of “success”, since they reflect the issues that challenge us and leave communities aware of the challenges to be taken on.

Finally, in relation to the role of the academic, the established tradition naturalises a unilateral and omnipotent role in the decisions, reflections and writing of research. Such a role places the researcher in a struggle for visibility and positioning, which is evident, for example, in calls for funding, awards, and institutional recognition. Subverting the expected prominence for the researcher, we implemented collaborative research and writing exercises authored by teachers and university students. We also decided to abstain from participating in institutional calls and research measurements, which has allowed us to open up to broad work agendas, not subordinated to pre-established terms of reference. This determination also allows us to do the research we want to do and not the trendy research that is applauded by the fashions of the moment, or just the research that is being paid by funding agencies.

This text intends to foster a discussion with MES colleagues on the singular experiences that they have lived in their own path, namely about the ways in which research groups are i) de-formed, ii) dis-organized and iii) dis-approved within their local communities. Such discussion can help the MES community to reflect about the conditions of possibility for research in mathematics education, and how some working notions (v.gr. *horizontalidad*,

plurality, etc.) can emerge. In short, we believe that to take a critical stance on the officially accepted practice of research is to take up a struggle for authenticity and independence.

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